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The Role of Crisis Management Strategies in Reducing Earthquake Damage

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Abstract

Everyone is aware of the role of natural disasters, especially earthquakes, in causing casualties and financial losses. One of the management requirements of a region, city, or even a country is to anticipate management measures to control the aftermath of an accident, referred to as crisis management. Human resource management (HRM), which is implemented to help the victims, is one of the main strategies after the earthquake. In this study, the theoretical foundations and literature on earthquake, crisis management, and HRM are reviewed. Besides, earthquake-prone areas in Tehran province (as a study area) are identified. To this end, the failure spectrum in the area is predicted by dividing the failure into complete rupture, very severe destruction, extensive destruction, and fast motion with high damage. The situation showed that the strength of the buildings must first be ensured so that they can be properly exploited after the earthquake. According to the situation in the area, the available human resources can be used to help the victims. Finally, solutions in the field of HRM after an earthquake are suggested, including training people, grouping them, forming crisis teams, specialized training for setting up shelters, and so on.

Keywords: earthquake, crisis management, crisis solutions, human resources.

1. Introduction

Natural disasters are among the problems that most cities in the world are grappling with. Earthquake is one of the characteristics of the planet and has caused many deaths and financial losses throughout the world. Earthquakes are one of the most well-known natural disasters in the world due to their vast territory and the extent and severity of the damage they cause. One of the most important factors that have a significant impact on increasing or decreasing human damage and casualties in the event of natural disasters is crisis management. This knowledge is referred to as a set of measures that are taken before, during, and after natural disasters to reduce the effects of these unexpected events. Urban planning can implement the necessary management principles to reduce the vulnerability of cities to these events by relying on geographical data and explaining its principles and concepts. When we talk about urban management, we mean that all institutions and organizations involved in organizing and living in the city should be under the supervision of single management to manage the city and create a calm and livable environment for citizens in a

balanced way away from inconsistencies and rework. Since Iran is located on a seismic belt and experiences various earthquakes from time to time, planning must be done to prepare for risk reduction before an earthquake occurs. This study is conducted to zone and identify sensitive areas near active earthquake faults in Tehran so that correct and rapid measures can be taken to reduce the life and financial losses of the earthquake.

2. Problem Statement

As a natural phenomenon, an earthquake is not just a disaster, but one of the most unavoidable natural events, causing the forces trapped in the earth's crust to be released and the crust to regain calm and stillness. The confrontation of human phenomena and man-made factors with this natural phenomenon turns it into a destructive catastrophe. Earthquakes cause great human and financial damage to human settlements, destroy long-term investments, and jeopardize the country's development. As gathering places for human populations, cities are no exception to the occurrence of these natural disasters. Serious measures need to be taken to reduce the vulnerability of these settlements to natural disasters. Tehran is one of the cities in Iran that faces this problem more than other cities. This metropolis is extremely vulnerable to natural disasters due to its geographical location, being located between the Alborz Mountains, the presence of rivers and streams within it, and being located on many faults. Another factor that aggravates the damage to the city is the presence of worn-out textures, which generally consist of small one- and two-story houses that are densely constructed next to each other. These houses often do not follow technical standards and are not sufficiently earthquake resistant. Another problem with these textures is their inadequate and limited access, which makes it difficult to provide relief to their residents after natural disasters and can exacerbate human catastrophe as conditions become more critical. Moreover, the lack of coordination between the organizations involved in the crisis in Tehran and problems such as the condition of quantitative and qualitative physical space have made the city more vulnerable to natural disasters (Gerami, 2014).

3. The Necessity of the Study

Iran is one of the most seismically active countries in the world due to its location in the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt, geological and tectonic position, the existence of numerous active faults, and the continuous occurrence of microearthquakes. Studies on seismicity and historical seismic events in the last two thousand years and analysis of instrumental data of the last century suggest that the country experiences many large and small seismic events continuously and is prone to large earthquakes in the future. On the other hand, vulnerability to possible earthquakes is constantly increasing as a result of the uncoordinated and unprincipled growth of most cities throughout history, especially during the last century. Construction in the area of faults, disregard for the seismic resistance of vital buildings and facilities, inhomogeneous and vulnerable expansion of the city texture, and many other things all indicate that irreparable losses and damages will occur in the event of a major earthquake in any of the cities. Bam (2003) and Manjil (1990) are objective evidence of these effects. Some of the other issues that can exacerbate such events are the lack of awareness and preparedness of the people and the inadequacy of the facilities and infrastructure required for crisis management. The statistics of earthquakes that occur within 200 km of the provincial capital show that earthquakes of different magnitudes occur every year and

that a devastating earthquake above 6 Richter occurs every seven years. According to official statistics, an earthquake of a magnitude less than 4 Richter occurs every day, an earthquake of magnitude 4 Richter occurs every month, three earthquakes of magnitude about 6 Richter occur every year, and an earthquake of magnitude 7 occurs every ten years in Iran in the last thirty years. Approximately 120,000 people have lost their lives in earthquakes from the Buin Zahra earthquake in 1962 to the Bam earthquake in 2003.

As the main center of activity in the country and with 19% of the total population (Statistical Center of Iran, 2006), Tehran is located in a very high-risk zone and is exposed to deadly and devastating earthquakes. According to the Iran Ministry of Roads & Urban Development, 11 cities in Tehran province have a relatively high seismic risk. These cities are Eshtehard, Tehran, Damavand, Rudehen, Rey, Fasham, Firuzkuh, Karaj, Mahdasht, Varamin, and Hashtgerd (Iran Newspaper, 2003, No. 2689).

4. Objectives

The main objective of this study is to identify areas prone to severe, moderate, and low destruction in earthquakes so that management decision-makers in the organizations can take appropriate measures by using human resource management in crises based on the proposed classification. In times of crisis, the efficiency of the road network can be assessed and the deployment of relief teams can be located only by identifying areas prone to severe and moderate destruction. This study focuses on the zoning of these areas.

5. Literature Review

A review of the relevant literature in recent years is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Literature on crisis management in recent years (Khammar, 2013)

Researcher	Title	Methodology	variables
Jamali and Fatehi Manesh (2010)	Effectiveness Of Crisis Staff Ojt (On Job Training) Appropriate Strategies on Enhancing the Earthquake Preparedness	Descriptive-analytical	Environmental-economic
Taghvaei and Darabi (2008)	Urban disaster management with an emphasis on the process after the disaster	Documentary-descriptive-analytical	Environment-human
Eftekhari and Badri (2003)	Economic Impact Assessment of Integrated Villages After Earthquake from Sustainable Development Viewpoint: A Study on Balkor and Jamalabad from-E Only County	Descriptive-analytical	Environmental-economic-social
Sayyah Mafazli and Sahafi (2010)	The Methodology Of Risk Management Model Within Crisis Management Of Municipal Area (The Case Study: Evaluation of Semi-Quantitive Risk And Radar Model In Determination of Risk	TOPSIS model	Environment-human

	Earthquake Amounts in 13Th Tehran Municipality)		
Rabbani (2010)	The Impacts of Micro Credits on Crisis Management in Iran: A Case Study of Rural Women Credit Fund in Poshtroud Village of Bam County	Library-descriptive-analytical	Environment-human
Chalook (2004)	Analysis of Current Security Status in Tehran: Offering Policing Strategy in Confrontation with an earthquake Crisis through using Swot Technique (Crisis Management)	Descriptive-analytical and SWOT model	Economic-social-environmental-human
Rakshani and Khammar (2015)	The Role of Crisis Management Strategies in Reducing Earthquake Damage (Case Study: Khorramabad)	Library-descriptive-analytical-field	Environmental-economic
Mousavi et al. (2011)	Urban Land Use Planning to Reduce the Damage Caused by Earthquakes with an Emphasis on the Emergency and Temporary Accommodation in Mahdasht	Documentary-descriptive-analytical	Economic-social-environmental-human
Mohammadi et al. (2012)	Crisis management and reducing the vulnerability of vital arteries in earthquakes in Zanjan province	Library-descriptive-analytical	Environmental-economic-social

6. The Study Area

In this study, the seismicity of Tehran province is examined. The position of Tehran province in zoning the seismic density of the country can be seen in Figure 1. According to the figure, Tehran is not in a critical position, but the presence of major and active faults in the north and south of the province (Figure 2) shows that there is still a risk in this province.

Figure 1. Zoning of the seismic density of the country

Figure 2. Major and active faults of the country

Furthermore, the province has many earthquake-prone areas in terms of seismic density. The areas can be seen in Figure 3. The major and active faults of Tehran province are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Earthquake-prone areas in the country

Figure 4. Major and active faults in Tehran province

7. Methodology

In this study, the library-documentary-analytical-descriptive method is used. In the theoretical explanation of the subject, data are collected by taking notes from books, papers, seminar results, projects, official statistics, doctoral dissertations, master's theses, official centers and institutions, and so on. Besides, the maps provided are extracted from the GIS database of the Iran National Cartographic Center. The area is first studied for GIS in terms of fault dispersion by using a natural substrate for zoning the city in terms of earthquake vulnerability.

The main purpose of this study is to determine the degree of vulnerability to earthquakes and provide appropriate solutions based on crisis management and the use of military human resources. The degree of vulnerability of areas to earthquakes is determined as follows:

- A) Probability of rupture: 700 meters in the anabatic section and 300 meters in the katabatic section;
- B) Very severe destruction: 3 km on both sides of the fault;
- C) Extreme shocks and extensive destruction: 7 km on both sides of the fault;
- D) D) Fast motion zone with high damages: 10 km on both sides of the fault;
- E) C) Zone with the possibility of soil liquefaction and severe destruction: in areas with sandy structures, water leaking from the ground and wells that sink at the same time with the structures (Mousavi, 2011).

Accordingly, the study methodology is the zoning of the study area according to the above, identifying earthquake-prone areas, and finally providing practical solutions.

8. Implementation

Earthquake-prone areas are extracted based on the relationships described in Methodology Section and are shown in Figure 6. According to the figure, a large part of the study area is prone to destruction and serious damage and requires special measures in crises. However, these areas are measured by the status of major and active faults, and some faults are inactive and may become active if little energy is released. They will lead to the development of vulnerability in all regions.

Figure 6. The extent of earthquake vulnerability in different areas of Tehran

9. Measures to Deal with the Crisis

The following measures should be taken in three stages: pre-crisis, intra-crisis, and post-crisis, based on the time cycle of the crisis:

A) Pre-crisis measures include the following:

Establishing executive committees, selecting executive committee members, collecting necessary data and statistics, developing optimal policies, approving codified policies, forecasting, and holding necessary training courses to prepare and act in case of emergency.

B) Intra-crisis measures include the following:

Announcing the crises, activating the executive committees, investigating the occurrence of crisis in different departments, operations command, crisis control and management, continuous crisis reporting, providing optimal solutions on how to operate, establishing coordination among employees, informing, and necessary warnings.

C) Post-crisis measures include the following:

Announcing the end of the crisis, estimating the consequences and damages resulting from the crisis, coordinating the collection of debris and waste in natural crises, preparing a financial list of financial, human, physical, and equipment damages, planning to repair the damage, restoring the routine, planning to prevent similar events in the future and the occurrence of secondary events, and recording and archiving documents and experiences of events.

10. Proposed solutions to the earthquake crisis in Tehran province to reduce financial and human losses

- A) Research on the prediction of time, place, type, and magnitude of the earthquake in the study area;
- B) Preparing a micro-zoning map for different areas of the city;
- C) Determining the technical methods of strengthening historical buildings;
- D) Assessing the vulnerability and damage of infrastructure facilities in the city in the event of an earthquake;
- E) Formulating basic strategies for the formation of a clear and orderly structure to manage the human resources of the army in the event of an earthquake;
- F) Holding beginner to advanced crisis management training courses for the army's human resources for earthquake management both during and after the earthquake;
- G) Classifying the army's human resources into different groups and performing continuous maneuvers to eliminate the shortcomings and weaknesses of people in the event of an earthquake;
- H) Forming crisis teams and determining the responsibility of individuals to assist the victims after the earthquake;
- I) H) Training the army's human resources to expedite the establishment of temporary camps for the victims.

11. Conclusion

As one of the most devastating natural disasters, earthquakes always cause loss of life and property. Earthquake damage can be significantly reduced by considering any solution to control the disaster before, during, and after the occurrence. Crisis management is one of the most complete solutions to deal with earthquakes. As the Islamic Republic of Iran Army is one of the key organizations serving the dear people of Iran, it can provide good assistance to the victims by relying on its human resources and managing and preparing them to be used in crises. This study first examined crisis, crisis management, and human resource strategic management (here the human resources of the Islamic Republic of Iran Army). It then determined the earthquake-prone areas in Tehran province and the areas that would suffer from rupture, very severe destruction, extensive destruction, and fast motion with high damage in the event of an earthquake. Due to the location of the main army barracks in earthquake-prone areas, these barracks should be secured against earthquakes to ensure their strength to provide shelter after the earthquake. Finally, solutions were proposed to use the army's human resources to deal with the earthquake, such as training courses, forming crisis teams, and so on.

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